

A Thermodynamic Study of Molecular Association by Gas-Liquid Chromatography : Trilaurylaminealcohol Systems

S. BHATTACHARYYA**, D. RANA and S. N. BHATTACHARYYA*

Polymer Science Unit, Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science, Jadavpur, Calcutta-700 032

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The results of interactions between trilaurylamine and four alcohols are presented. A method of calculation has been proposed for the specific retention volumes in a particular alkane liquid phase without actually carrying out the glc experiments with the said alkane. The equilibrium constants obtained, though large, are systematically so and are consistent among themselves and the ΔH values determined from these are the anticipated ones and seems to be as good as those obtained by any other method.

Martire-Riedl method^{1,2} or the neat liquid method is simpler of the two glc methods for studying hydrogen bonding interaction as it necessitates less time and less experiments. But the Cadogan-Purnell method^{3,4}, called the solution method is more general in its scope of application. This technique is in agreement with broad methodology of studying such interaction by traditional spectroscopic and calorimetric methods where solutions of different strengths of the components in an inert solvent are used. In Martire-Riedl method, on the other hand being a neat liquid method, no substance can be used here as the solvent phase which is capable of self-association. The other disadvantage with the Martire-Riedl method is that for each donor studied in the column, one has to study an inert alkane solvent of the same size, molar volume and polarisability. For example, to study association of trilaurylamine-alcohol systems, the neat inert alkane liquid phase in which specific retention volumes of the alcohols are to be determined would have to be hexatriacontane (n-C₃₆H₇₄). It is known that for straight-chain alkanes, a chain length of over seventeen or eighteen makes the alkane solid around room temperature. The higher alkanes have a much higher melting point making them incapable as solvent phases at the temperature at which association phenomena are usually studied. In this communication, we report an attempt that has been made to develop a method so that one can calculate the specific retention volumes of a solute in an alkane liquid phase from a knowledge of specific retention volumes of the same solute in other alkanes.

Let us look briefly at the problems of extrapolation first. It is known that specific retention volume, V_g^0 is directly related to the partition coefficient, K ,

$$K = V_g^0 \rho_l T / 273 \quad (1)$$

where, ρ_l is the density of the liquid phase. From the phase equilibrium thermodynamics, K is also given by

$$K = c \exp(-\Delta H_s / RT) \quad (2)$$

in which the solution process usually is exothermic (ΔH_s negative) and increasing T reduces K . From equations (1) and (2) one obtains the temperature dependence of V_g^0 ,

$$\log V_g^0 = -(\Delta H_s / 2.303 RT) + C_1 \quad (3)$$

If and only if we assume a small temperature interval, the variation of the product of the liquid phase density and absolute temperature in equation (1) can be assumed small and may be included in the constant C_1 of equation (3). ΔH_s also is taken as constant over short temperature ranges. Hence, a plot of $\log V_g^0$ vs $1/T$ over short temperature range is linear which has been verified experimentally^{5,6}. It has been found that upto within a temperature interval of 50° the linearity is maintained. This is true with data presented in our earlier work⁷ as well as the data reported by others^{1,8,9}. However, it is to be noted that when the extrapolation has to be made over a wider temperature range this method is not acceptable. Moreover, the V_g^0 's determined experimentally at higher temperatures are themselves liable to be comparatively inaccurate due to the smaller retention times. The melting point of hexatriacontane being 75.7°, it is necessary to derive some indirect method to obtain specific retention volumes in that alkane which is required for calculating the association parameter in trilaurylamine (TLA) in the temperature region 30–60°. Also, in view of the above discussion, any attempt to extrapolate the values obtained experimentally around 80° and above, to lower temperature appears inadvisable. We have made an attempt here to calculate the V_g^0 's for hexatriacontane from a knowledge of V_g^0 's of some lower alkane solvents for the same solutes in the temperature range 30–60°.

Pierotti *et al.*¹⁰ related the activity coefficient of the solutes to the structure of solvents and solutes. They found experimentally that activity coefficients γ can be given by

$$\ln \gamma = f(a) + f(b) + f(c) + f(d) + f(e) + f(g) \quad (4)$$

where the five function $f(b)$ to $f(g)$ are function of n_1 and n_2

**Present address : Department of Chemistry, Vidyasagar College, Calcutta-700 006.

which are the number of carbon atom in the solvent and the solute respectively. $f(a)$ includes all interactions not involving n_1 or n_2 but involving characteristic groups of the solvent and solute. If the solvent (stationary phase) is called R_1-X_1 and solute R_2-X_2 then the forces acting on the solute in its own liquid may be expressed as the sum of all possible interactions of R_2 and X_2 in pairs and the forces acting on the solute in the solvent may be expressed as the sum of all possible interactions of R_1 , R_2 , X_1 and X_2 in pairs. The function specified above could then be written with interactions involved and their dependence on carbon number of the solute and solvent. Pierotti put $f(a) = A$, $f(b) = B n_2/n_1$, $f(c) = C/(n_2 + C')$, $f(d) = D (n_2 - n_1)^2$, $f(e) = E n_1/n_2 = 0$ and $f(g) = G/(n_1 + G')$. A to G are constants and are to be empirically determined. The relation above is most general which simplifies to a much simpler form if the system (solute-solvent) is simple. Thus if the stationary phase (1) is given and if the solute (2) are a series of n -alkanes then $f(a)$ and $f(g)$ are both constant and C is equal to zero as this interaction involves two characteristic groups and the solute (R_2-X_2) which is absent now. D as given by the relation of Bronsted and Koefoed¹¹,

$$\ln \gamma = -D(n_1 - n_2)^2 \quad (5)$$

is of the order of 10^{-4} . For ranges of n_2 not spanning more than 10 carbon atoms $f(d)$ can be regarded as constant. Under such conditions, the general equation of Pierotti *et al.*¹⁰ reduces to

$$\ln \gamma = A + B n_2/n_1 \quad (6)$$

where A is now a composite constant. Herington¹², however, pointed out that equation (6) can be derived independently. We assume that equation (6) will also be valid for the alcohol solutes used here. Conversely, when a solute is given and γ values are to be determined in a series of high molecular weight alkanes, the problem is essentially the same and the simplified equation (6) may be used. The activity coefficient of a solute, with the correction factors of nonideality can be written as

$$\ln \gamma = \ln \frac{273 R}{V_g^0 p_2^0 M_1} - \frac{p_2^0}{RT} (B_{22} - v_2) \quad (7)$$

where, p_2^0 is the vapour pressure of the solute, M_1 the molecular weight of the solvent, B_{22} the second virial coefficient of the solute probe in the gas phase and v_2 the molar volume of the pure solute probe in the liquid state. For a particular solute at a particular temperature, the second term of right-hand-side of equation (7) is constant. On rearrangement, equation (7) reduces to

$$\ln \gamma = \ln C_1 - \ln (M_1 V_g^0) \quad (8)$$

where, C_1 is a constant. By combining equations (6) and (8) we obtain,

$$-\ln (M_1 V_g^0) = A_2 + B n_2/n_1 \quad (9)$$

A plot of $\ln (M_1 V_g^0)$ against $1/n_1$ would then be linear for a

particular solute in several alkane solvents, and from the slope and the intercept V_g^0 could be calculated for the same solute for a different alkane solvents of known M_1 and n_1 . To check the validity of the proposed method of calculation we have calculated the specific retention volume of several solutes in n -C₁₇H₃₆ and n -C₁₈H₃₈. The experimental specific retention volumes of those solutes were obtained from the work of Tewari *et al.*¹³ for three alkane stationary phases, n -C₂₄H₅₀, n -C₃₀H₆₂ and n -C₃₆H₇₄ at 76° and $\ln (M_1 V_g^0)$ against $1/n_1$ was plotted as shown in Fig. 1. As predicted, the plots were found linear. The V_g^0 's were calculated for the solutes at 76° for stationary alkane phases of n -C₁₇H₃₆ and n -C₁₈H₃₈. The V_g^0 's at 30, 40, 50 and 60° were then calculated by extrapolation using equation (3). These are then compared with existing data. Table 1 gives the calculated and experimental specific retention volume of three alkane solutes. The experimental values are those from the work of Martire *et al.*^{1,8}. It appears that the agreement is quite reasonable (within $\pm 2\%$ on an average) although we are at the limits of extrapolation here.

TABLE 1—COMPARISON OF EXPERIMENTAL AND CALCULATED SPECIFIC RETENTION VOLUMES (V_g^0 , ml g⁻¹) OF THE ALKANE SOLUTES

Liquid phase	3-Me-pentane Exp/ (Calcd.)	2,3-Di Me-butane Exp/ (Calcd.)	2,2-Di Me-butane Exp/ (Calcd.)	Temp. °C
n-C ₁₇ H ₃₆	343.2	279.4	198.3	30
	(350.1)	276.6	200.1)	
	236.2	195.0	141.9	40
	(237.0)	195.1	141.1)	
	165.5	138.9	102.3	50
	(163.1)	138.7	101.4)	
n-C ₁₈ H ₃₈	119.7	101.5	75.95	60
	(119.1)	98.9	75.1)	
	332.4	271.7	—	30
	(332.2)	265.9	190.4)	
	231.0	191.1	—	40
	(226.3)	188.2	134.9)	
	164.2	137.3	—	50
	(156.8)	134.2	97.7)	
	119.1	100.7	—	60
	(114.9)	96.0	72.7)	

The relation (9) was used in calculating the specific retention volume of four alcohols (*viz.* n -propanol, n -butanol, isobutanol and *sec*-butanol) and three nonpolar alkane solutes (*viz.* 3-methylpentane, 2,3-dimethylbutane and 2,2-dimethylbutane) in hexatriacontane. V_g^0 's for the corresponding solute in heptadecane, octadecane (obtained from Martire *et al.*^{1,8}), nonadecane and tetracosane (our earlier work⁷) were known and V_g^0 's in the hexatriacontane were obtained by least-square best fit of the equation (9). The V_g^0 's calculated are given in Table 2.

Fig. 1. Plot of $\ln(M_1 V_g^0)$ vs $1/n_1$ for a particular solute at 76° for three alkane systems : (■) 3-methylpentane, (▲) 2,3-dimethylbutane and (●) 2,2-dimethylbutane.

Results and Discussion

Infinite dilution V_g^0 values were obtained at 30, 40, 50 and 60° for four alcohol solutes (viz. n-propanol, n-butanol, isobutanol and sec-butanol) and three nonpolar alkane solutes (viz. 3-methylpentane, 2,3-dimethylbutane and 2,2-dimethylbutane) on four columns of trilaurylamine of different liquid weight fractions (f). Plots of V_g^0 vs f^{-1} indicated that the retention volumes were independent of the liquid load of the columns. The average of the four V_g^0 's was taken as the value at the infinite dilution bulk specific retention volume. The values of the V_g^0 are presented in Table 2. The maximum standard deviation of V_g^0 is within 1%.

In Table 3 the values of $\bar{V}_g^{0a} / \bar{V}_g^{0b}$, activity (a_D) and activity coefficient (γ_D) are given. With these values and the result from Table 2, the association constant (K) were determined as prescribed in our earlier work⁷. The values of K are given in Table 4. It has been estimated that the probable error in the calculated V_g^0 in hexatriacontane is within 2% and considering the other sources of error, the maximum probable error in the K values reported are within 5%. The ΔH and ΔS for association were found out

from the least-square best fit of the linear plot of $\ln K$ vs $1/T$. The ΔH and ΔS values are given in Table 5 along with the corresponding standard deviation.

TABLE 2 - INFINITE DILUTION BULK SPECIFIC RETENTION VOLUMES (V_g^0 ml g⁻¹) IN HEXATRIACONTANE AND TRILAURYLAMINE AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Solute Component	30°	40°	50°	60°
In hexatriacontane :				
n-Propanol	57.99	42.48	31.71	24.27
n-Butanol	173.8	118.2	82.23	58.63
Isobutanol	122.2	84.93	60.11	43.44
sec-Butanol	114.6	76.82	52.61	37.05
3-Methylpentane	170.9	123.8	91.8	68.87
2,3-Dimethylbutane	155.3	112.2	82.51	61.63
2,2-Dimethylbutane	100.5	75.15	57.88	44.92
In trilaurylamine :				
n-Propanol	1192	704.1	417.1	260.3
n-Butanol	3872	2146	1217	719.4
Isobutanol	2484	1444	854.9	527.5
sec-Butanol	1402	813.2	485.9	301
3-Methylpentane	174.4	123.3	91.25	67.12
2,3-Dimethylbutane	156.6	113.3	81.77	60.66
2,2-Dimethylbutane	104.1	77.47	58.64	45.19

TABLE 3 - ACTIVITY (a_D), ACTIVITY COEFFICIENT (γ_D) OF THE ELECTRON DONOR AND $\bar{V}_g^{0a} / \bar{V}_g^{0b}$ OF TRILAURYLAMINE-ALCOHOL SYSTEMS AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURE

	30°	40°	50°	60°
$\bar{V}_g^{0a} / \bar{V}_g^{0b}$	0.979	0.988	1.001	1.012
a_D	1.661	1.663	1.599	1.569
ρ_D	1.054	1.044	1.031	1.019

TABLE 4 EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANT (K , dm³ mol⁻¹) OF TRILAURYLAMINE-ALCOHOL SYSTEM AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURE.

	30°	40°	50°	60°
n-Propanol	11.53	9.41	7.61	6.28
n-Butanol	12.52	10.37	8.64	7.27
Isobutanol	11.38	9.67	8.27	7.19
sec-Butanol	6.61	5.79	5.12	4.60

Though the equilibrium constants (Table 4) appear to be large, nevertheless they are quite consistent between themselves considering the inductive and steric effects of different alcohols. The trend in K values with different alcohols is almost the same as that for the tri-n-octylamine-alcohol systems⁷. The ΔH values (Table 5) are in order with values usually obtained for N...H-O bonds^{14,15}. Moreover, the trend in ΔH values with the four alcohols appears to be the anticipated one considering the inductive and steric effects of the alcohol molecules. The parallelism between the ΔH and ΔS values, reported by Pimentel and McClellan¹⁴ and as observed in the cases of other donors⁷, is also present in this system (Table 5).

TABLE 5—ENTHALPY AND ENTROPY OF FORMATION OF TRILAURYLAMINE-ALCOHOL COMPLEXES AT THE TEMPERATURE RANGE 30–60°

	$-\Delta H$ (kcal mol ⁻¹)	$-\Delta S$ (cal mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)
n-Propanol	4.07 ± 0.07	8.57 ± 0.22
n-Butanol	3.63 ± 0.02	6.98 ± 0.05
Isobutanol	3.07 ± 0.02	5.31 ± 0.05
sec-Butanol	2.43 ± 0.03	4.26 ± 0.10

Experimental

The experimental technique for the determination of the infinite dilution bulk retention specific volumes in trilaurylamine was same as with other electron donors studied in an earlier work⁷. $V_g^{0'}$'s obtained were corrected for adsorption of the solute on the solid support-liquid phase interface and the gas-liquid interface as described earlier⁷. These were then plotted against the reciprocal weight fraction f^{-1} of the liquid phase. In case of trilaurylamine (TLA) the plots were found to be independent of liquid loading.

Liquid phases : Trilaurylamine (TLA) was used as liquid phase. Hexatriacontane (n-C₃₆H₇₄) was chosen as the reference alkane solvent. However hexatriacontane was never used in the actual experiment and results thereof were calculated as described. Very close $V_g^{0'}$'s obtained for both trilaurylamine and hexatriacontane at all the temperatures justify our choice of reference alkane and also the method of calculation.

TLA, obtained from Societe des Usiness Chimiques, Paris, was further purified by vacuum distillation and stored in a dark-coloured bottle. The densities of TLA determined by accurate pycnometry at 30, 40, 50, 60 and 70° were found to be 0.823, 0.816, 0.810, 0.804 and 0.797 respectively.

Solutes : Seven solutes were used : n-propanol, n-butanol, isobutanol, sec-butanol, 3-methylpentane, 2,2-dimethylbutane and 2,3-dimethylbutane. The alcohols (A.R.) and three alkanes (Aldrich; 99% purity) were used as such.

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